

Cyclization of Naphthalene-1,8-Dicarboxaldehyde with Nitromethane

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Aromatic and aliphatic dialdehydes (1,4; 1,5 and 1,6) undergo with nitroalkanes cyclization under the action of strong bases to furnish nitroderivatives with 5, 6, and 7-membered rings^{1,2,3}. In the case of the aromatic dialdehydes the condensation with nitromethane is accompanied by a direct dehydration².

Lichtenthaler *et al.* have found that the condensation of naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxaldehyde (I) with nitromethane in the presence of different strong bases does not take place, because (I) undergoes with the base a 1,5-intramolecular hydride ion shift (Cannizzaro-reaction)^{4,5}.

During the course of our studies of this reaction it was found that large dilution of the reaction mixture depresses the Cannizzaro-reaction to a great extent and promotes the cyclization with nitromethane.

It was found that naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxaldehyde (I)* reacts with nitromethane in a dilute solution of dioxan methanol mixture in the presence of 1*N* sodium methoxide at room temp. for 8 hrs. to give a primary cyclization product of *aci*-nitrosalt (II). Neutralization of (II) with mineral acids leads to direct dehydration and the formation of (III).

The NMR-spectrum of (III) in CDCl_3 showed a multiplet at τ 2.45 indicating six aromatic protons plus one olefinic proton. Another signal appeared at τ 4.22 corresponding to an aliphatic proton.

The IR-spectrum of (III) showed two absorption peaks at 1580 cm^{-1} and 1340 cm^{-1} characteristic for the nitro-group, and another absorption peak at 3500 cm^{-1} due to the $-\text{OH}$ stretching vibration.

EXPERIMENTAL

M.p. was uncorrected and was measured on a Kofler hot bench, Reichert Wien instrument. Microanalysis was carried out by Janssen Pharmazeutica Research Laboratory, Beers, Belgium.

* (I) In the crystalline state exists in the cyclic hemialdal form⁶.

NMR-spectrum was measured on Varian A 60 A in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal reference. IR-spectrum was taken on Helger and Watt H 800.

1-Hydroxy-2-nitro-peri-naphthene (III): A dilute solution of 1.0 g naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxaldehyde (I) (obtained by the *meta* periodate oxidation of *cis*-acenaphthene-diol-1,2)⁶ in 300 ml dioxan containing 50 ml absolute methanol was treated with one ml nitromethane. A solution of 1 *N* sodium methoxide (3 ml) in 50 ml absolute methanol was added dropwise with cooling in ice. Stirring was continued for 2 hrs., 500 ml of water was added, and the mixture was neutralized with 1 *N* hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixture was then left overnight at room temp., the product obtained was washed with water, dried over P_2O_5 , and recrystallized from chloroform, yellow needles, m.p. 210° . Yield 0.1 g, 10%. (Found: C, 69.02; H, 3.57, N, 6.16; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 68.76; H, 3.99; N, 6.02%).

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REFERENCES

1. H. H. Baer and H. O. L. Fischer, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., USA*, 1958, **44**, 961; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5184; A. C. Richardson and H. O. L. Fischer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1132.
2. F. W. Lichtenthaler, *Angew. Chem.*, 1964, **76**, 84; *Angew. Chem. internat. Ed.*, 1964, **3**, 211; H. H. Baer, *Angew. Chem.*, 1963, **75**, 1124.
3. F. W. Lichtenthaler and H. K. Yahya, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, **23**, 1805; *Chem. Ber.*, 1967, **100**, 2389; 1968, **101**, 908; *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1967, **5**, 485.
4. F. W. Lichtenthaler and Abdu El-Scherbiney, *Chem. Ber.*, 1968, **101**, 1799.
5. F. W. Lichtenthaler, H. Leinert and H. K. Yahya, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1966, **21b**, 1004.
6. Dissertation H. K. Yahya, T. H. Darmstadt 1966.